

Promotion as a Catalyst for Employee Performance in First City Monument Bank in Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The major advocacy of this study is Promotion as a Catalyst for Employee Performance in First City Monument Bank (FCMB), in Abia State, Nigeria. It is observed that the decision to package the promotion model of FCMB in line with the organization's best-place-to-work philosophy is geared towards identifying, inspiring and rewarding excellence and hence, a way of rewarding productivity, and employees who have brought huge levels of innovation, and those influential in the development of new services and solutions which provide speed and convenience to the customers.. The study found out that promotion limits the influx of fresh perspectives and new ideas into FCMB which may prevent external candidates with expert knowledge from joining the organization. The study recommends among others that it is crucial for FCMB to communicate transparently about promotion processes and criteria, provide constructive feedback to employees who were not promoted, and foster a supportive and inclusive work culture. The study concludes that it is crucial for FCMB to have performance-enhancing system capable of facilitating the best management and development of their employees, and increasing their competitiveness so that there will be a correlation between promotion and employee performance.

Keywords: *Promotion, Employee, Performance, Productivity, Training*

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Introduction

Employees are a driving force of every organization and their welfare must be given uppermost attention. One of the key issues that concern every worker in an organization has to do with the promotion. Promotion system may differ from one organization to the other and may change from time to time. This arguably makes motivation of employees the most complex of all management functions (Bowen & Radhakrishna, 2010). However, a basic feature of promotion is that it must cause employees to give their best to the organization. As Lucey (2014) puts it, "a properly organized and well planned reward structure, benefits both the firm and its employees". We are all different; our needs, thoughts and experiences are different and we are all motivated by different things.

Organizations are seeking ways to beat the competition and be profitable. Nothing is more critical to this goal than human energy - a strategic approach to motivating the total organization (Daft, 2003). Armstrong (2003) concludes that when managing the performance of teams and

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individuals, both inputs (behaviour) and output (results) need to be considered. That is, performance of the organization cover competency levels and achievements as well as objective setting and review. Bourne (2003) recognizes employees as one of the most important stakeholders in their five facets of the performance prism. This supports Balmer and Gray's (2000) assertion that the key for an organization to stay competitive is the ability to attract and retain skilled and motivated employees. Retaining rare skills and knowledge from the labour market requires implementation of a rational promotion structure. All organizations are concerned with what should be done to achieve sustained high levels of performance through people. This means giving close attention on how individuals can best be motivated through promotion.

Thus, First City Monument Bank (FCMB) maintains its headquarters in Lagos - Nigeria's financial capital and largest city. As of July 2012, it maintains over 310 networked branches in all 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, making it the 7th largest Nigerian bank, by branch network.

For the year ended December 31, 2023, FCMB Group Plc grew deposits, loans, assets under management, revenue and earnings and improved its environmental, social, and corporate governance scorecard. The Group recorded a profit before tax of ₦104.4 billion, a 186% year-on-year (YoY) increase compared to ₦36.6 billion in 2022 and earnings growth across its business segments: Banking Group 212.6%, Consumer Finance 67.3%, Investment Management 40%, and Investment Banking 89.7%. The Group's total assets increased by 48.3% from N2.98 trillion to N4.42 trillion at the end of December 2023.

FCMB's customer base grew by 15.6% YoY from 10.9 million to 12.5 million for the period ended December 2023, whilst users of its mobile app that offers lending, wealth and payment solutions grew by 31% YoY to 3.4 million. Similarly, the Bank's agency banking network grew to over 164,000 agents. With an enlarged customer base, an expanded distribution platform, and the use of artificial intelligence to automate and optimize loan underwriting processes, the Group successfully disbursed over 1.5 million loans worth N100.8 billion to individuals, N14.4 billion to micro-enterprises and N177.9 billion to SMEs during the period (FCMB Press Release, 2024).

FCMB promotion structure is well-known for maintaining high standards of professionalism and excellence, where exceptional performance, innovation and hard work are recognized and rewarded (Saunders, 2018). The decision to package the promotion model in line with the organization's best-place-to-work philosophy is geared towards identifying, inspiring and rewarding excellence and hence, a way of rewarding productivity, and employees who have brought huge levels of innovation, and those influential in the development of new services and solutions which provide speed and convenience to the customers (Mckenzie & Shilling 2018).

FCMB accommodates flexible working hours and employees could be deployed or redeployed to branches and offices close to their homes. The Group pays attention to promoting and preserving quality time for its employees to spend with family and loved ones. FCMB now has a shutdown policy, which mandates branches to shut down at 7pm. It is to ensure that employees do not stay late in the office (Merchant, 2007). Weekend assignments are not encouraged and where unavoidable, an employee is not supposed to work more than one Saturday per month. (Nelson & Economy, 2005). Promotion in FCMB is based on performance of employees, multi task/duty and years of service.

In FCMB, promotion is seen as just one of our ways of rewarding productivity, and employees who have brought huge levels of innovation, and those influential in the development of new products and solutions which provide speed and convenience to the customers. It is part of the Group's tradition of rewarding and motivating employees for higher productivity. FCMB value the contributions of our employees, and their recent promotions are aimed at motivating employees and creating new avenues for career growth within the institution".

It is worthy to note that effective and efficient promotion may not reduce the rate employee leave FCMB. Employees may decide to leave to where they are not forced to work, where there is lack of undue supervision and unnecessary pressure at work. Sometimes employees leave for reasons that are somewhat beyond an organization's control. They leave because there are better opportunities elsewhere. What makes these opportunities more appealing to employees who are progressing well in their career? It depends on the employees. Some want more autonomy, while others want to substantially increase their compensation plan. Some employees may have much more confidence in another organization's leadership team, or be interested in joining a high growth company with a disruptive offering. And sometimes, employees may leave for practical reasons, such as less time spent traveling. Hence, promotion matters may not be why employees leave FCMB to other banks (FCMB Press Release, 2024).

FCMB in Abia State is a large financial services provider, offering retail banking, corporate banking and investment banking services to large corporations, small and medium enterprises, as well as individuals. It has branches in Aba (the commercial nerve centre of the state) and Umuahia - the State capital (Sarantkos, 2005). FCMB in Abia State has two departments- Operation or Service Department and Sales or Marketing Department.

Statement of Problem

Promotion in FCMB is fraught with daunting challenges that needs conscious, conscientious and meticulous navigation so that the organization can bring out the best from its employees to be able to compete effectively in the competitive market. Consequently, promotion does not guarantee that all necessary skills and knowledge for the new role are already present within the organization. While employees may excel in their current positions, they may lack specific competencies required for higher-level roles (Alston, 2023).

Promotion may limit the influx of fresh perspectives and new ideas into the organization. External candidates often bring diverse experiences and alternative viewpoints that can drive innovation and challenge the status quo. Promotions can sometimes lead to internal dynamics and office politics. Employees who were not promoted may feel overlooked or undervalued, resulting in decreased morale and potential conflicts within the team (Alston, 2023).

Salaries of the staff at the lower cadre are not commensurable with their current promotion status because of the salaries of executives and senior staff members that are too large for the present income generated by the bank to sustain, and usually their salaries are tied to direct performance target and no targets are assigned to such outrageous salaries (Bourne, Franco & Wilkes, 2003). The aggregate of these salaries engulf most income made by the bank as the task of this group of staff do not add any form of financial value that commensurate to their pay. They are rated by group performances rather than by individual performance contribution. The present promotion model in use in FCMB is toxic to the health of the bank (Bohlander, 2001). There is need for senior staff pay cut or assignment of business targets that will at least justify their monthly salaries, or even implement the duo to revert the present status so that the salaries of every staff will reflect the promotion given to them irrespective of the cadre employees.

Research Questions:

1. What are the challenges associated with employee promotion in of FCMB?
2. Does lack of promotion significantly affect employee productivity?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine promotion as a catalyst for employee performance in First City Monument Bank in Abia State, Nigeria. While the specific objectives are:

1. To ascertain the challenges of FCMB in promoting its employees
2. To find out if lack of promotion significantly affect employee productivity

Hypotheses

The study will be guided by following hypotheses:

1. Employee promotion in FCMB is associated with some challenges.
2. Lack of promotion significantly affects employee productivity

Literature Review

The Concept of Promotion

Promotion is evidence of recognition of employee performance. Someone who promoted will be considered to have a good performance on the job. Promotions are very important for the company, because the promotion means the stability of the company and employee morale will be more assured. Promotion can affect employee satisfaction, Kosteas (2007) said hopes to be promoted to have a strong role. Employees who are aware that they will never be promoted will degrade its performance, until they think there will be opportunities to be promoted in the future. Pergamit and Veum (1989) also says that by setting and increase the likelihood of promotion will increasingly affect employee satisfaction. In addition to other factors of job satisfaction, job satisfaction is determined by satisfaction with the promotion. Compensation to be one of the main factors of personnel because compensation will affect employee job satisfaction, such as the opinions expressed Mangkunagara (2009) which says that the compensation given to employees is very influential on the level of job satisfaction, and performance. Thomas Patton (1977) explains that the compensation must consider several aspects such compensation must be done in a balanced and fair, should be sufficient and accepted by the employees. Provision of compensation is something that must be considered seriously because the financial rewards are among the factors that resulted in employee satisfaction (Kreitner and Kinicki (2006).

An overview of performance

Performance has been diversely defined by a wide-ranging experts and authorities with different attributes but is strongly linked to corporate efficiency. Daft (2003) defines Company's performance as the organization's ability to attain its goals by using resources in an efficient and effective manner. Armstrong (2003) noted that performance is a multi-dimensional construct, the measurement of which varies depending on a variety of factors. Performance can be seen as a record of outcomes achieved as well as a person's accomplishments. Performance can therefore be regarded as behavior –the way in which organizations, teams and individuals get work done. Armstrong (2003) concludes that when managing the performance of teams and individuals both inputs (behavior) and output (results) need to be considered. Performance management covers competency levels and achievements as well as objective setting and review. The concept of performance is an old phenomenon in a working environment especially in the private sector. If you cannot define performance, you cannot measure or manage. Daft (2003) sees performance as a process, which entails a number, or series, of behaviours, directed towards the achievement of some predetermined goal. The Oxford English dictionary defines performance as the "accomplishment, execution, carrying out, and working out of anything ordered or undertaken".

Armstrong and Murlis (1994) argue that "performance is a multi-dimensional construct, the measurement of which varies, depending on a variety of factors." They also state that it is important to determine whether the measurement objective is to assess performance outcomes or behaviour. That is one should distinguish between outcomes (results/output) and behaviour (the process). According to Armstrong and Baron (op. cit.) performance as defined above is affected by a number of factors, including the following: (a) personal factors - the individual's skill, confidence, motivation and commitment. (b) Leadership factors - the quality of encouragement, guidance and support provided by the managers and team leaders. (c) Team factors - the quality of support provided by colleagues. (d) System factors - the context of work and facilities (instruments of labour) provided by the organization; and (e) Contextual (situational) factors - internal and external environmental pressures and changes. All these factors should be taken into account when measuring performance for pay decisions. Traditional approaches to performance appraisal attribute variations in performance to personal factors, when, in fact, they could actually be caused in part or entirely by situational or systems factors (Atkinson and McCrindell, 1997). Essentially, the assessment of individual performance must necessarily consider not only what individuals have done (the results), but also the circumstances in which they have had to perform (Jaghult, 2005). This assessment process should extend to the performance of the manager as a leader, because what the performer does is mainly a reflection of the manager's behaviour in terms of on-the-job training, coaching and guidance. Nelson and Economy (2005) argues that determinants of job performance are knowledge, skill and motivation factors. In his model of performance, Nelson and Economy (2005) argues that the three variables have a functional relationship the impact of which determines or influences an individual's performance.

Theoretical Framework

The Human Relations Approach

The human relations approach / movement of the neo-classical theory was triggered off by the famous research of Elton Mayo and his team conducted at the Western Electric Company, Hawthorne, Illinois Plant; Chicago, between 1923 to 1926 and 1927 1932.

Mayo sharply debunked the grandiose claims of the scientific management, which saw man as an economic animal who would respond to financial and material incentives. The human relations approach clearly departed from this idea and ushered in the new preoccupation with worker motivation, participation, satisfaction, and the like. Its primary aim was the determination of the factors that significantly influence the efficiency and productivity of workers.

The human relations approach did not reject totally the importance of financial incentives on output but argued that this is not their (workers) first concern. Sometimes they are more interested in the way their superiors treat them, good working environment, they like to be praised, know what is expected of them, where they stand in relation to their boss' expectations; they like to feel independent, express their feelings, listened to, consulted and given a sense of belonging. All these constitute socio-psychological factors, which automatically will influence productivity. The human relations theory has heavy orientation to sociology and psychology. Their primary focus is the humans in the organization as socio-psychological beings, and in fact, what may motivate them to put in their best to enhance output. People are seen in the organization as socio-psychological beings, and in fact, what may motivate them to put in their best to enhance output. They get them to do it. She urged organizations to stop suppressing the differences that may arise within their boundaries, and rather seek to integrate those differences, thereby allowing them to contribute to the organization's growth and development (Nwachukwu, 1999).

Discussion

Hypothesis One: Employee Promotion in FCMB is Associated with Some Challenges

Promotion does not guarantee that all necessary skills and knowledge for the new role are already present in an organization. While employees may excel in their current positions, they may lack specific competencies required for higher-level roles (Alston, 2023). Promotion may limit the influx of fresh perspectives and new ideas into the organization. External candidates often bring diverse experiences and alternative viewpoints that can drive innovation and challenge the status quo. Promotions can sometimes lead to internal dynamics and office politics. Employees who were not promoted may feel overlooked or undervalued, resulting in decreased morale and potential conflicts within the team (Alston, 2023).

Salaries of the staff at the lower cadre are not commensurable with their current promotion status because of the salaries of executives and senior staff members that are too large for the present income generated by the bank to sustain, and usually their salaries are tied to direct performance target and no targets are assigned to such outrageous salaries (Bourne, Franco & Wilkes, 2003). The aggregate of these salaries engulf most income made by the bank as the task of this group of staff do not add any form of financial value that commensurate to their pay. They are rated by group performances rather than by individual performance contribution.

The present promotion model in use in FCMB is toxic to the health of the bank (Bohlander, 2001). There is need for senior staff pay cut or assignment of business targets that will at least justify their monthly salaries, or even implement the duo to revert the present status so that the salaries of every staff will reflect the promotion given to them irrespective of the cadre employees. This discussion supports our first hypothesis that employee promotion in FCMB is associated with challenges,

Hypothesis Two: Lack of Promotion Significantly Affects Employee Productivity

Promotion and productivity are inextricably bound together, hence, they are inseparable. Any organization that wants its employees to put in their best should endeavour to promote them as at and when due. This is because, promotion creates an opportunity for the promoted individual to inspire other employees not yet promoted to be more productive, take on new roles, and improve their abilities and capability to help the organization achieve its goals. When the right employees are promoted, other staff may feel its impact and become more motivated and more productive

However, promoting the right people is arguably a rigorous task, and organizations must employ the principle of meritocracy in terms of years of service, qualification and performance in written and oral examination and test.

More so, promotions lead to new responsibilities and require the development of employee potentials. However, these elements do not only apply to the promoted employee. Other employees may also benefit from the promotion.. When other employees observe those promoted have engendered a paradigm shift, they may also be motivated to emulate them. This situation may, in turn, improve the overall work environment and increase the productivity of both the employee and the organization. From the above analysis, we therefore accept the second hypothesis that lack of promotion significantly affects the employee productivity.

Findings

From the discussions above, the study found out that:

1. In FCMB, promotion does not commensurate with employee performance, because of the fact that they lack the requisite knowledge to operate at the level of their newly promoted cadre.

2. Promotion limits the influx of fresh perspectives and new ideas into FCMB which may prevent external candidates with expert knowledge from joining the organization
3. There is no transparency and criteria for promotion.
4. Some promotions are not based on merits but on cognitive melodrama(favouritism).

Recommendation

In the light of the fore-going, the study recommends as follows:

1. Organizations should ensure that employees' performances are improved through training, seminars and conferences.
2. It is crucial for FCMB to communicate transparently about promotion processes and criteria, provide constructive feedback to employees who were not promoted, and foster a supportive and inclusive work culture.
3. There ought to be a "window" to accommodate experts from around the world to take full time, part time or consultancy roles whenever the need arises so that they can bring their experiences into the organization.
4. Promotions should be based on years of service, qualification and performance in a competitive written or oral test/examination.

Conclusion

There is need for FCMB to develop an all-encompassing and transparent promotion model showing the basis of promotion which should be made known to every employee. The result of any promotional examination or test should not be hidden. It is crucial for FCMB to have performance-enhancing system capable of facilitating the best management and development of their employees, and increasing their competitiveness so that there will be a correlation between promotion and employee performance. Across the core areas of human resource, promotion is one of the most crucial matters in the management literature. It is commonly believed that if standard promotion model is implemented with bias, employee will be motivated to work hard which will have a positive effect on the organizational productivity.

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